

E-RIHS IP

European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science IMPLEMENTATION Phase

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D4.2 Marketing Strategy for Boosting E-RIHS Services

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ABSTRACT

The E-RIHS ERIC Marketing Strategy is conceived to support the operational phase of this research infrastructure by supporting the establishment of effective marketing for its service portfolio. It draws on the principles outlined in the forthcoming E-RIHS ERIC Business Plan 2025-2027 and other relevant policy documents, which provide details on the E-RIHS ERIC service offer and access modes.

This deliverable “D4.2 Marketing Strategy for Boosting E-RIHS Services” of the E-RIHS IP project identifies the key elements of a marketing strategy for E-RIHS ERIC, the main markets and the market trends in heritage science and cultural heritage domains, and describes potential avenues for creating awareness of the RI services, attracting talented users, and promoting a culture of access to E-RIHS in the Heritage Science communities of practice. The strategy distinguishes different marketing approaches and communication channels, based on the various types of RI-services offered, also with consideration of the different modes of access to the various services and of the various remits/areas of impact, including research, communities of practice, museums, scholars, and industries. It further provides a series of strategic recommendations for actions, based on the analysis of the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats for the E-RIHS marketability template. A priority is set for the establishment of SMART Key Performance Indicators to assess the effectiveness of the marketing action, in the context of a more general monitoring and evaluation framework of E-RIHS performance. While E-RIHS service access is not market-driven at this time, suggestions for industry engagement are provided, which can be implemented in time, as the E-RIHS services become sufficiently standardised and industry-ready. The objective of this marketing strategy is to underpin the medium- to long- term sustainability perspectives for E-RIHS, with a consistently high interest of its stakeholders, including internal and external users from the public sector, and the attraction of novel users and/or co-creators from the private sector.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ACRONYMS	EXPANSION
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AR	Augmented Reality
ARCHLAB	ARCHive LABoratory: E-RIHS access platform that brings together organized scientific information in largely unpublished datasets from archives of prestigious European museums, galleries and research institutions (https://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-catalogue-of-services/)
CCSI	Cultural and Creative Sectors and Industries
CH	Cultural Heritage domain
CNN	Committee of National Nodes of E-RIHS
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
DIGILAB	DIGital LABoratory: E-RIHS access platform that provides remote access to heritage science data, supplemented with digital services and tools within a virtual research environment (under development)
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
E-RIHS PP	E-RIHS Preparatory Phase
EC	European Commission
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
ERC	European Research Council
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures
FIXLAB	FIXed LABoratory: E-RIHS access platform that brings together fixed research facilities and associated scientific experience of their staff that develop and maintain sophisticated state-of-the-art instrumentation for advanced diagnostics and archaeometry (https://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-catalogue-of-services/)
GA	General Assembly of E-RIHS
HBIM	Heritage Building Information Modelling
HS	Heritage Science
HS Academy	E-RIHS training program in heritage science delivered through various formats, including doctoral summer schools, on-site training camps, webinars, lecture series, and specialized modules. The program is designed for both E-RIHS users and providers.
IIIF	International Image Interoperability Framework
ISO	International Organization for Standardisation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MF	Monitoring and Evaluation Framework

MOLAB	Mobile LABORatory: E-RIHS access platform that brings together European laboratories offering state-of-the-art mobile equipment and related competencies, for in-situ non-destructive measurements of artworks, collections, monuments and sites (https://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-catalogue-of-services/)
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
RSS	Really Simple Syndication
SMART KPI	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound, which are the five criteria that a KPI must meet to be considered a SMART indicator
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
VR	Virtual Reality
WG	Working Group

INTRODUCTION AND CONTEXT

Marketing strategies are critical documents to the success of the broader business plan implementation. When such strategies are ineffective and marketing goals are not met, an organisation development may be hindered, ultimately affecting its sustainability. Although other factors can influence an organisation's sustainability, marketing strategies play an immediate and pivotal role in driving or hindering progress. To be effective, marketing strategies must be aligned with the organisation's goals, culture, and operational context. Marketing strategies cannot be produced in isolation; their goals need to be well-integrated into the organisation's overall objectives and business planning for optimal effectiveness.

E-RIHS is the *European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science*, created to support the research community on heritage interpretation, preservation, documentation, innovation and management. E-RIHS is currently in its implementation phase. **In the context of E-RIHS, marketing denotes all promotional activities aimed at ensuring that its services are efficiently and impactfully taken up by users. These include advertising and market research, i.e., research related to the needs and requirements of the heritage sector.**

The nexus between cultural heritage and cutting-edge technology has exceptional prospects for understanding, preserving and enhancing the material legacy of humanity (Furferi et al., 2024). The cultural heritage sector includes a significant variety and complexity of data and information. Making this accessible today represents one of the main aims of cultural institutions. The connections between digital archives and knowledge enable the extension of this wealth of information beyond the physical existence of cultural assets (Nappi et al., 2024). Research findings reveal a number of difficulties and limitations with regard to communicating and understanding the value of heritage (Cerquetti & Ferrara, 2018). Strategic support is needed to enhance the knowledge exchange, the promotion of research collaboration, to facilitate practitioners in knowledge translation skills and to leverage the participation of users (Katrakazis et al., 2028).

The lessons learned from the revision of the *E-RIHS Business Plan* (Nardello, Strlič, & Virgili, 2023; D4.1 of E-RIHS IP) have informed the development of such a strategy, in the form of a marketing strategy, with the aim to offer clear perspectives to E-RIHS ERIC and organise the marketing practices that will characterise its operational phase, providing indications to meet the above-mentioned challenges of the HS research market. This marketing strategy further draws from the considerations emerged from other deliverables of E-RIHS IP, among which are the following: D5.8 *E-RIHS ERIC User Strategy* (Heritage, 2024); D6.4 *Report on Cooperation Activities* (Castillejo & Carmona, 2024); D6.2 *Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Strategy of E-RIHS ERIC* (Benassi et al., 2024); D4.5 *Revised E-RIHS Training Strategy* (Andrews & Grau-Bove, 2024); and D5.6 *Access Policy* (Etgens, Laclavetine & Petitcol, 2024).

1. LESSONS LEARNED FROM THE E-RIHS BUSINESS PLAN REVISION

The following information and gaps, outlined in the revision of the *E-RIHS Business Plan v.1.01 (2020)* within E-RIHS IP D4.1 (Nardello, Strlič, & Virgili, 2023), have been updated as of the drafting of this deliverable and utilised to inform the E-RIHS Marketing Strategy.

1.1 The main stakeholders

The stakeholders of E-RIHS are public, representing national, regional and EU level interests; private stakeholders are also represented, in the form of not-for-profit entities (e.g., foundations and associations). Private organisations and industries are much less invested; among these, SMEs are the most represented. A stakeholder mapping for E-RIHS ERIC has been developed and included in Annex I.

1.2 Governance

E-RIHS will become a legal entity in the form of an ERIC in the course of 2025. An *ad interim* governance is in place, with representation of both the Member Countries (the Interim General Assembly, iGA), the heads of the operations at the national level (Committee of National Nodes, iCNN), and an executive director (Director General, iDG). The E-RIHS Central Hub staff is under discussion within the iGA. Before the ERIC's establishment, staff will be provided by National Nodes on a temporary assignment under official travel status; once established, the ERIC will rely on staff through in-kind contributions, secondments, or direct hiring. A Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board is planned within E-RIHS ERIC governance but not yet established. While no innovation committee is foreseen, E-RIHS is developing the *Agenda for Smart Future Innovation* to align medium- and long-term priorities, including technological upgrades. An in-house research programme remains under discussion.

1.3 Main activities and research programmes

In terms of the main activities carried out by E-RIHS, the most important and implemented are service provision, research projects and training. With the E-RIHS IP project, E-RIHS has developed an Access Policy to its services (Etgens, Laclavetine, & Petitcol, 2024). Currently, service provision is exclusively enabled through excellence-driven access to the three physical platforms (ARCHLAB, FIXLAB and MOLAB). A virtual platform (DIGLAB) is under construction to enable wide access. Proposed access modes include limited commercial access, specifically market-driven access for economic sector, alongside matchmaking service for routine and exploratory research and thematic calls for access to address research needs identified by E-RIHS or initiatives like the *European partnership Resilient Cultural Heritage* and other EU-funded projects (e.g., ERC, MSCA).

In terms of training E-RIHS provides short-term training events (e.g. summer schools, training camps) and lecture series through the E-RIHS Heritage Science Academy. Other activities concern the organisation of training for users, providers, and managers as well as for researchers from across the Nodes (Andrews & Grau-Bove, 2024).

1.4 Monitoring: Key performance indicators (KPIs)

Among the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) E-RIHS already has in place, the ration of access provided to access requests is considered a top priority, while user satisfaction and quality/SOPs-Standard Operating Procedures are regarded as high priorities. Publications and IP generation, while medium priority, are essential for establishing E-RIHS prominence in the heritage science domain, and a recommendation to monitor this through a dedicated KPI has been included in this Marketing Strategy. Units of access allocated to users are currently a lower priority and not monitored, but calibrating their optimal allocation could provide economic benefits. As such, a recommendation to monitor this aspect through a dedicated KPI has also been included. Other KPIs, such as annual turnover, staff retention and number of service contracts, are not less important and must be implemented. The low attention to the annual turnover is an indication that this organisation considers its economic sustainability beyond the mere monetary value; rather, the value E-RIHS generates is represented by the quality of access provision and its user satisfaction. This perspective aligns closely with E-RIHS's mission and vision (E-RIHS ERIC Scientific and Technical Description, v. 5.02, 2022).¹ This strong self-identification trait may be further reinforced and clarified to a value proposition, emphasising the unique benefits E-RIHS delivers to its stakeholders.

1.5 Service provision

The most important services that E-RIHS offers include access to its facilities, training and research services. In terms of service provision, E-RIHS has a booking system for its available services, but a transparent pricing policy is not yet in place. Data-related services could be further strengthened. These services could even have a strong internal market, and be supported by public funds, given the importance of Open Science and FAIR data practices for the new EU ERA, as well as the role advocated by the EC for ESFRI RIs to champion the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative. From a commercial perspective, consultancies could also be offered towards private users as well as public users.

1.6 Output: Non-financially evaluated products

E-RIHS considers that its long-term scientific impact builds on the previous EU projects (EU-ARTECH, CHARISMA, IPERION CH and currently IPERION HS) and highlights a total of 397 publications with over 6.393 citations (Clarivate WOS consulted 1 December 2024).² On the other hand, papers citing

¹ *Excerpt from the E-RIHS ERIC Scientific and Technical Description, v. 5.02 (2022):* E-RIHS vision is to ensure that heritage remains meaningful, relevant, and accessible in a diverse and changing world for the benefit of present and future citizens. E-RIHS uncovers the cultural and historical layers embedded in heritage, seeks optimal ways to preserve it by understanding material changes, and harnesses its potential as a source of socioeconomic and environmental sustainability. The mission of E-RIHS is to serve the heritage science community of both scholars and practitioners by providing access to world-class facilities and expertise, delivering interdisciplinary and intersectoral training, promoting open science and FAIR principles in cultural heritage, enhancing service value through user-provider co-creation, stimulating open innovation in heritage practices, and integrating cutting-edge EU facilities to form an unique organization that is recognized and plays a significant role in the domain worldwide. Through all these efforts, E-RIHS seeks to increase the impact of heritage science for the benefit of society.

² This data will be included in the regular E-RIHS quality audit evaluations under the E-RIHS ERIC quality system.

“E-RIHS” are relatively few, as expected from the young development stage of the RI. The establishment of a brand and the shaping of the access policy shall facilitate the acknowledgment of the RI in the research product generation and ultimately provide an instrument to measure some dimensions of its impact. Training-related activities are either based on events or on hands-on training during individual access projects. Training provided via summer schools and training camps under the framework of IPERION HS attracted a significant number of graduate, postgraduate and PhD students, totalling 193 students. Additionally, an average of 24 students per year, either as PI or part of user groups, requested IPERION HS research services, with circa 40% (around 10 students annually), being granted access.

1.7 Output: Financially evaluated products

At the moment, financially evaluated products are limited to training and contract research, followed by IP and licensing. Access to facilities as well as to data resources and related services, and the creation of spin-offs are under-represented because, among other cultural reasons, a guiding policy is currently missing. A marketing strategy is defined here in order to build a culture of producing financially evaluated products in addition to non-financially evaluated ones, to the extent desirable.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE E-RIHS MARKETING STRATEGY

With the goal of building a community around E-RIHS, composed of scientists, practitioners, policy makers, industries and the general public, the overarching objectives of this strategy are outlined in the table below.

Table 1. E-RIHS Marketing Strategy Objectives

Marketing Strategy Objective Number	Objective Description
MS01	Increase E-RIHS ERIC visibility.
MS02	Support the establishment of the E-RIHS prominence in the heritage science field, in activities of research, development, training, innovation, and evidence-based policies, for the advancement of the cultural heritage sector, at the national, EU and international levels.
MS03	Promote the state-of-the-art E-RIHS services to ultimately increase the number of its users and the uptake of its services.
MS04	Support the structuring of a reference community of practices around E-RIHS ERIC, including stakeholders and users from academia, cultural institutions, industry, policy sector, and the general public.
MS05	Strengthen the effectiveness of the E-RIHS ERIC distributed model by establishing a monitoring framework with KPIs tied to target performance values and time boundaries (see Annex III).
MS06	Establish a culture that includes producing financially evaluated products in addition to non-financially evaluated ones, to the extent desirable.

In Annex IV, the marketing strategy implementation plan contains examples of KPIs that could support measuring the success in reaching these objectives.

3. KEY ELEMENTS OF THE E-RIHS MARKETING STRATEGY

3.1 The E-RIHS Mission and Objectives

The core mission of E-RIHS ERIC is enabling, through research and innovation, an improved understanding and sustainable preservation of heritage objects and sites (Strlič & Virgili, 2024; E-RIHS IP *D4.3 Revised E-RIHS Business Plan*). The major objectives include:

- Securing state-of-the-art, excellence-driven, open access for researchers in academia, cultural institutions and industry to the four access platforms: ARCHLAB, DIGILAB, FIXLAB and MOLAB;
- Developing common practices, protocols and an interoperable ecosystem of tools, methods, resources and data for the research in heritage science, contributing to the establishment of the EOSC and to its use by heritage science researchers;
- Fostering an inclusive interdisciplinarity approach, outreaching to all the communities of users across traditional disciplinary boundaries, and establishing a new attitude based on interoperability, knowledge exchange and defragmentation of research initiatives;
- Supporting the interdisciplinarity approach of heritage science by fostering excellent training of the next generation of heritage scientists;
- Creating a global player by building on the internationally leading status of the European heritage science, reaching a worldwide community of users (E-RIHS ERIC Scientific and Technical Description, v. 5.02, 2022).

3.2 E-RIHS Value Proposition

The value proposition of E-RIHS ERIC lies in its structural feature of integrating an array of state-of-the-art equipment, resources and expertise of its personnel distributed across Europe into a unified and coordinated infrastructure. This framework amplifies the impact of heritage science by accelerating scientific achievements and translating them into real-world applications for the study, preservation and appreciation of cultural heritage. By combining cutting-edge facilities, innovative methods and multidisciplinary knowledge, E-RIHS optimises access and delivers tailored solutions to complex heritage challenges. In doing so, it creates value for scholars by offering advanced research opportunities, practitioners by equipping them with new effective practices, and society by contributing to its cultural and socioeconomic development. Beyond providing access services, E-RIHS embeds open science principles, user-provider co-creation, training and innovation into its operations. Through its efforts, E-RIHS strengthens the relevance of heritage science worldwide and ensure its legacy for future generations of scholars, practitioners, and stakeholders.

3.3 E-RIHS Marketability

In alignment with the E-RIHS mission, objectives and key stakeholders, this strategy builds the marketing narrative around a clear value proposition that encapsulates the key marketable features of E-RIHS. They include:

- **Uniqueness of technology and service offering:** A unique research infrastructure combining expert knowledge providers, state-of-the-art facilities, advanced digital resources (forthcoming) and collaborative environment facilitating co-creation between users and providers, to support cutting-edge research and innovation in heritage science;

- **Research driven by excellence:** A commitment to excellence in research, ensuring user satisfaction through high-quality Standard Operating Procedures;
- **Specialised support services:** Service provision supported by uniquely experienced teams in heritage science, enhancing researchers and practitioners to increase their effectiveness in research production capacity;
- **Advanced training:** to support the development of cutting-edge expertise enabling the absorption of knowledge in a field that is inherently interdisciplinary and intersectoral;
- **Centralised access:** A single-entry point for all E-RIHS services, offering visibility on all the steps of the users' research project;
- **Open and FAIR:** Open sharing of best practices, recommended methodologies and unique heritage science digital resources; aligned protocols for experimental research practices and (meta)data archiving, throughout Europe, and beyond.

3.4 E-RIHS as a Platform for Innovation through Co-Creation

E-RIHS ERIC fosters a culture of exchange and cooperation in a safe and ethically responsible research environment. The combination of the skills and knowledge of E-RIHS facilities operators with the scientific curiosity of its users naturally generates collaborative research endeavours and new collaborative projects resulting in innovative results. The user feedback is also an essential mechanism to stimulate innovation in the E-RIHS service offer and management effectiveness. This **co-creation practice** is one of the basic paradigms of E-RIHS, leading to a continuously evolving value of E-RIHS for both users and providers of services, ultimately being at the heart of the RI sustainability.

3.5 E-RIHS Quality Standards and Certifications

ISO-standard quality management practices and Good Laboratory Practices are meant to guide an organisation and ensure that the RI management and its facilities adhere to stringent quality standards in their operations. E-RIHS does not hold such certifications however E-RIHS shall implement the quality manual which emphasises consistency by applying uniform operational standards across all National Nodes and prioritising the evolving needs of users and stakeholders through active engagement and feedback (D3.5; Doherty, Andrews & Virgili, 2024). Such practices can greatly enhance the value of E-RIHS to its users and can be a marketing asset and selling point.

3.6 E-RIHS Instrumentation and Services

- ARCHLAB, MOLAB, FIXLAB, and DIGILAB

The physical platforms of E-RIHS encompass facilities, resources and services, as well as the expertise and experience of the E-RIHS teams operating them. They are ARCHLAB (physical and local digital collections), FIXLAB (large scale facilities accessible at fixed locations) and MOLAB (mobile instrumentation). A unified Catalogue of Services (CoS) and dashboard has been available to users since 2020, providing an integrated single-entry point to all platforms, whereby users can follow their projects from the proposal to the exploitation phase. A digital platform, DIGILAB, will be established in the near future, offering a Virtual Research Environment and advanced research services to users, adhering to FAIR, Open Access, and EOSC principles.

- HS Academy

The Heritage Science Academy is a platform for engagement with users particularly through training and dissemination activities, both in-person and remotely. It is aimed at users, access providers and infrastructure managers. The HS Academy currently offers:

- Webinar and lecture series;
- Focussed courses, including training camps and doctoral summer schools;
- User meetings.

3.7 The E-RIHS Ethos and Brand

- Excellence-based
- Science-curiosity driven, limitedly market-driven
- Corporate identity established and its use regulated

E-RIHS ERIC ethical principles duly consider individual and collective responsibilities towards cultural heritage, ensuring its preservation for present and future generations, as well as towards society and the environment. Adherence to the ethical principles is strictly expected within the E-RIHS ERIC and in all organisations working under the E-RIHS label.

The ethical policies of E-RIHS ERIC focus on sustainability, open access to knowledge and data developed using public funding and responsible innovation, which form the basis of the E-RIHS Ethics Guidelines (see D3.5; Doherty, Andrews & Virgili, 2024). Each user and provider of E-RIHS ERIC will be required to read the Guidelines and abide by their principles. Promoting diversity is at the core of E-RIHS ERIC. Equal opportunities are actively promoted, and diversity is valued. Scientific excellence can only be achieved if each individual is evaluated based on talent, ability, competency, and qualification.

Although scientific research in E-RIHS ERIC is guided by curiosity and freedom to pursue knowledge, responsibility towards cultural heritage and cultural organisations requires a collaborative approach and respect for institutional objectives that may be different from those of researchers and research organisations. This is a direct practical implication of working with cultural heritage and a core area of expertise of E-RIHS partners and includes respect for cultural values, and the implementation of appropriate procedures for ethical handling and sampling of cultural heritage.

In keeping with its ethical principles, E-RIHS ERIC does not directly engage in the authentication of works of art and artefacts. While scientific research can be used in authentication, the provision of authentication expertise is not part of the remit of E-RIHS ERIC. E-RIHS ERIC further follows the recommendations of the European Textbook on Ethics in Research when applicable (EC, 2010).

4. MARKETS FOR E-RIHS, TRENDS AND OUTLOOK

4.1 Main Markets for E-RIHS

Heritage science offers diverse applications that can be effectively harnessed by various markets, utilising advanced technologies and methodologies to improve operations, enhance services, and foster deeper engagement with cultural heritage. The following markets stand out for their potential to benefit from heritage science applications.

- **Conservation and restoration sector**
 - *Exploitation potential:* This sector can leverage heritage science to enhance restoration techniques and improve conservation outcomes. Technologies like 3D printing, chemical analysis, and non-destructive testing allow conservators to restore artifacts with precision, reduce handling risks, and develop tailored conservation strategies.
 - *Applications:* 3D printing for replicas, hyperspectral imaging for material analysis, non-destructive testing tools, structural analysis of heritage buildings, advanced materials for restoration.
- **Museums and cultural institutions**
 - *Exploitation potential:* Museums and cultural institutions can leverage heritage science outcomes to improve conservation methods, expand research capabilities, and enrich visitor experiences. Non-invasive techniques such as hyperspectral imaging and 3D scanning allow for detailed analysis without damaging artifacts. Digital archives and interactive exhibits enhance educational outreach and audience engagement, making collections more accessible to a global audience.
 - *Applications:* Digital archives, 3D modelling and scanning, interactive exhibits, conservation tools.
- **Education and academic institutions**
 - *Exploitation potential:* Schools, universities, and training centres can integrate heritage science into curricula and research programs. By using advanced technologies like digital modelling, VR simulations, and AI-driven data analysis, educational institutions can provide hands-on learning experiences and innovative research opportunities in fields such as archaeology, history, art conservation, and cultural studies.
 - *Applications:* Virtual reality classrooms, digital reconstruction software, AI tools for historical research, online learning platforms.
- **Architecture and urban planning**
 - *Exploitation potential:* Urban planners and architects can use cultural heritage science to integrate historical preservation into modern development projects. Tools like Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Building Information Modelling (BIM) help document and manage heritage buildings and sites. This allows for sustainable urban development that respects cultural heritage while modernizing infrastructure.
 - *Applications:* GIS mapping, HBIM (Historical Building Information Modelling), digital reconstruction of urban landscapes, heritage impact assessments.
- **Government and heritage agencies**
 - *Exploitation potential:* National and local governments, cultural ministries, and heritage agencies can exploit heritage science to manage and preserve national heritage sites and artifacts more effectively. These organisations can use data-driven tools for heritage site

management, disaster preparedness, and digital archiving, supporting sustainable tourism and cultural promotion.

- *Applications:* Digital databases, heritage management software, disaster risk assessment tools, public engagement platforms.

- **Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and international bodies**

- *Exploitation potential:* NGOs and international organisations like UNESCO can use cultural heritage science to support their missions in cultural preservation, education, and heritage management. These entities can employ advanced diagnostic and monitoring tools, develop capacity-building programs, and use digital platforms for cultural promotion and awareness campaigns.

- *Applications:* Digital inventory systems, capacity-building tools, public awareness campaigns, international collaboration platforms.

- **Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and philanthropy**

- *Exploitation potential:* Corporations engaged in CSR initiatives and philanthropic efforts can support cultural heritage projects as part of their social responsibility strategies. This support can include funding for digital preservation projects, sponsoring exhibitions, and investing in educational programs related to cultural heritage.

- *Applications:* Funding for digital preservation projects, sponsorship of heritage exhibitions, partnerships with cultural institutions for CSR initiatives.

- **Tourism**

- *Exploitation potential:* The tourism sector can benefit from heritage science to enhance visitor experiences at heritage sites. Technologies like augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) can provide immersive tours and interactive guides, making historical and cultural narratives more engaging. By incorporating digital storytelling and multimedia content, tourism operators can attract more visitors and provide richer, educational experiences.

- *Applications:* Virtual tours, interactive maps, augmented reality apps, and digital guide systems.

- **Construction**

- *Exploitation potential:* The construction industry uses heritage science services ranging from archaeological prospection and preventive archaeology, as a legal requirement in many countries. It needs access to cutting-edge knowledge to develop technologies and materials compatible with heritage buildings and monuments, as well as to respond to new requirements related to energy efficiency and carbon footprint.

- *Applications:* Archaeological services, HBIM, new materials and technologies.

- **Digital and media companies**

- *Exploitation potential:* Companies specialising in digital content, gaming, and media production can use cultural heritage science to create culturally rich and immersive content. For example, game developers can incorporate accurate historical settings and narratives using data from heritage science, while media companies can produce documentaries and interactive experiences based on 3D reconstructions of historical events or sites.

- *Applications:* Historical video games, immersive VR experiences, digital storytelling, interactive documentaries.

- **Art market and private collectors**

- *Exploitation potential:* The art market, including galleries, auction houses, and private collectors, can benefit from heritage science applications, e.g., characterisation of

constituent materials and production techniques, for preservation of artworks and their evaluation. Techniques such as infrared spectroscopy, X-ray fluorescence, and digital imaging help in the analysis of art pieces, ensuring their authenticity and aiding in the proper maintenance and restoration of valuable items.

- *Applications:* Digital imaging for provenance research, dating, condition assessment tools.

- **Entertainment, cultural and creative industries**

- *Exploitation potential:* The entertainment industry, including film, television, and creative arts, can exploit cultural heritage science for authentic set design, costumes, and narratives that reflect historical accuracy. By using digital reconstructions and AR/VR, filmmakers and artists can create realistic and immersive environments for storytelling, contributing to a deeper cultural understanding and appreciation.

- *Applications:* Film set design, VR/AR for production design, historical accuracy in scripts and storytelling.

- **Publishing and media outlets**

- *Exploitation potential:* Publishers and media outlets can use heritage science to create engaging content that educates and informs the public about historical and cultural topics. This includes producing books, articles, and documentaries that draw on new research and technologies to tell stories of cultural heritage in novel ways.

- *Applications:* Interactive eBooks, documentaries, digital articles, podcasts focused on heritage topics.

In summary, multiple markets including conservation, museums, education, architecture, government, NGOs, digital media, entertainment, tourism, publishing, and Corporate Social Responsibility, can exploit cultural heritage science applications to enhance their services, preserve cultural assets, engage audiences, and promote cultural understanding and sustainability.

E-RIHS has a unique opportunity to position its marketing strategy within this realm of market possibilities. The likelihood of entering those markets should be tested and shape the strategy, with a mixture of avenues to be pursued: some bringing to the lowest-hanging fruits for immediate returns; some higher-road pursuits leading to a probable relevant impact on outstanding societal challenges.

4.2 Market Trends and Outlook

The integration of cutting-edge technologies into the field of cultural heritage presents exceptional opportunities for research, preservation, and promotion. Advanced technological tools, such as non-invasive imaging techniques, machine learning, artificial intelligence (AI), virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) have transformed the way cultural heritage is understood, preserved, and experienced.

Research Advancements: Technologies like hyperspectral imaging and deep convolutional neural networks are revolutionising cultural heritage research. Such techniques allow for the non-destructive analysis of materials, helping researchers identify and understand the components and degradation processes of heritage items.

Preservation Techniques: Non-invasive technologies, such as hyperspectral and multi-spectral imaging, provide valuable insights into the composition and condition of cultural artifacts, allowing conservators to develop targeted preservation strategies. The use of 3D printing, or additive manufacturing offers innovative solutions for creating replicas of damaged or missing components

of heritage structures. These replicas can be used to test conservation treatments before applying them to original artifacts, minimizing the risk of damage.

Interdisciplinary Collaboration and Innovation: Information and Communication Technology (ICT)-based devices encourage collaboration among researchers, archaeologists, conservators, and other stakeholders. Open-access repositories and 3D digital models facilitate group involvement in preservation projects, leveraging collective expertise. The creation and sharing of digital catalogues and ontologies further support this collaborative effort, enabling the effective organisation and dissemination of knowledge across different domains.

Engagement and Accessibility: VR and AR applications allow users to experience immersive journeys to ancient civilizations and interact with cultural items in unprecedented ways, not just visually, but also in tactile, olfactory and other ways. These technologies, enhanced by AI, make cultural heritage more accessible to a broader audience, enhancing engagement and education.

Emerging Technologies and Future Prospects: The adoption of AI and machine learning is gaining momentum in cultural heritage research. These technologies analyse large datasets, interpret complex patterns, and provide new insights into historical collections and environments.

In conclusion, the application of advanced technologies is reshaping the field of cultural heritage, providing new methodologies for research, innovative tools for preservation, and enhanced ways to promote and experience cultural assets. These technologies not only protect and preserve the material legacy of humanity but also foster a deeper understanding and appreciation of cultural heritage among diverse audiences, paving the way for future advancements in the field.

These insights provide a clear case for E-RIHS's sustainability and growth potential and can be regarded as the stepping stones of the E-RIHS services marketability.

5. SETTING PRIORITIES FOR THE E-RIHS MARKETING STRATEGY

5.1 SWOT Analysis of E-RIHS Marketability

In research infrastructures (RIs), a marketing strategy often has unique elements compared to traditional commercial organisations, as RIs serve a more specialised community, typically focused on scientific research, academia and public goods.

Some common elements of a marketing strategy tailored to RIs can be reflected in the following actions:

- Stakeholder engagement and relationship building, in particular collaboration with academia and industry and involvement of funding bodies;
- Promotion of research capabilities and services, for example, access to resources and data;
- Education, training, and capacity building, such as knowledge transfer between RI and academic or industry partners;
- Building a strong scientific reputation with peer-reviewed publications and citations and participation in international projects;
- Visibility through outreach and communication, for example with events and conferences;
- Digital marketing and online presence, e.g., with website and social media;
- Commercialisation and revenue generation with technology transfer, spin offs, consultancy;
- Branding and value proposition with a focus on mission-driven value proposition.

SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats) analysis is a strategic planning tool used to help organisations or individuals assess their internal and external environment (Sammut-Bonnici and Galea, 2015). Weaknesses and strengths depend on internal factors, the former are represented by disadvantages or challenges while the latter by advantages. Opportunities and threats arise from external influences and they depict external factors that could be leveraged for growth or improvement and external factors that could cause problems or risks.

An analysis of the E-RIHS SWOT in terms of achieving its marketing potential has been drawn (Table 2), considering the lessons learned from E-RIHS business plan revision (D4.1; Nardello, Strlič & Virgili, 2023) as well as the market trends and outlook for E-RIHS, and the above-mentioned elements.

Table 2. SWOT Analysis of E-RIHS for Harnessing its Marketing Potential.

STRENGTHS	OPPORTUNITIES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Governance expressing shareholders and stakeholder ▪ Established user community ▪ Uniqueness of service offer ▪ Positive feedback from user ▪ Training and educational offer ▪ Defined access policy ▪ Established branding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Become a champion for the realisation of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative ▪ EOSC HS thematic node leader

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Pursue novel application sector: New European Bauhaus³ related sectors and cultural and creative sectors ▪ Emerging technologies (AI-powered services, AR/VR technologies) ▪ The nodes/local organisations as actors of the marketing strategy ▪ Obtain philanthropic support (e.g., Fondazione CR Firenze) ▪ Strengthen relationships with SMEs and other commercial entities, including equipment co-ownership/leasing
<p>WEAKNESSES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Catalogue of Services under construction ▪ Service-uptake KPIs not fully developed ▪ Marketing budget not established ▪ Lack of an impact manager ▪ Market-driven access deprioritised 	<p>THREATS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sister-RI competition for new services ▪ Inability to evaluate the progress of the organisation towards its objectives, with risks for the long-term sustainability of E-RIHS, if a monitoring framework is not put in place ▪ Exclusive dependency on public funding

5.2 Marketing Strategy Priorities

On the basis of the lessons learned from the E-RIHS IP deliverables informing the elaboration of this strategy, and the SWOT analysis presented in the previous section, a series of recommendations have emerged, setting the strategic marketing implementation priorities for E-RIHS, as follows:

(1) Leveraging strengths and maximise opportunities:

- Establishing a budget for the marketing strategy – a suggestion for breaking down the costs is provided in Annex II;
- Establishing a monitoring framework for E-RIHS’ marketing activity performance, through a set of KPIs, that will be Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound (SMART). Each KPI shall be paired with clear target values, timelines, description of information sources, and potential information providers, ensuring a robust data collection and a transparent reporting mechanism. While some KPIs have been identified by previous deliverables (D6.4 by Castillejo & Carmona, 2024; D5.3 by Doherty, Andrews & Virgili, 2024), monitoring the performance of E-RIHS in its fundamental dimensions, such as the utilisation of available units of access, by both internal and external users, should be prioritised; a monitoring framework template is provided in Annex III;
- Engaging new users for existing and upcoming platforms, by implementing the user engagement strategy and the communication strategy detailed in the respective E-RIHS IP deliverables (D5.8 by Heritage, 2024; D6.2 by Benassi et al., 2024);
- Engaging scientific and commercial co-creators for innovation of services and maintaining a state-of-the-art infrastructure;

³ https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/index_en

Improve the access framework for the training offer (HS Academy), as detailed in *D4.5 Revised E-RIHS Training Strategy* (Andrews & Grau-Bove, 2024).

(2) Leveraging opportunities and overcome weaknesses:

- Positioning E-RIHS as a leader in the SSH RI ecosystem, following the recommendations of *D6.4 Report on Cooperation Activities* (Castillejo & Carmona, 2024);
- Positioning E-RIHS as a leader for a thematic node in HS data services, in the EOOSC ecosystem;
- Cultivate philanthropic contacts to support the E-RIHS mission.

6. MARKETING OUTCOMES

The tables below (Tables 3 and 4) present the expected outcome from the implementation of the marketing strategy, per practitioner sector, with suggestions for related marketing-strategy implementation-action types and channels. While the first pertains to the current E-RIHS users, described in other deliverables of this project (D5.8 by Heritage, 2024), the second regards the prospected user communities.

A suggestion for a marketing plan based on this strategy is provided in Annex IV.

Table 3. Marketing Strategy Outcome Pathways for Current E-RIHS Users.

Fields/Sectors	Practitioner Type	Service/Action	Implementation Channels	Desired Outcome
Social Sciences and Humanities	Curators, conservators, heritage managers, and scholars	Collaborative research	Cross-disciplinary projects, access to platforms, consultancies	New collaborative projects, service uptake
Built Environment	Building surveyors, facility managers, construction engineers, and climate scientists	Specialised workshops and fieldwork integrating new analytical methods	Consultancies, cross-disciplinary projects	Alliances, partnerships
Palaeontology and Palaeoanthropology	Researchers in anthropology, palaeontology, DNA studies, and taphonomy	Specialised workshops and fieldwork integrating new analytical methods	Cross-disciplinary projects, training, access to platforms	New collaborative projects, service uptake
Archaeology	Curators, conservators, heritage managers, and scholars	Collaborative research	Cross-disciplinary projects, access to platforms, training	Skills development, new projects, service uptake

Table 4. Marketing Strategy Outcome Pathways for Prospected E-RIHS Users.

Domain	Practitioner Type	Service/Action	Implementation Channels	Desired Outcome
Digital Heritage and Data Science Specialists	Digital scientists and data stewards	Digital preservation and computational analysis	Access to platforms, consultancies	Federation of digital repositories
Environmental Science	Scientists	Specialised workshops and fieldwork	Cross-disciplinary events, access to	Novel service users, service innovation

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Domain	Practitioner Type	Service/Action	Implementation Channels	Desired Outcome
		integrating new analytical methods	platforms, consultancies	
Educational Institutions and Junior Researchers	Post-graduate students and early-career researchers	Internships and educational programmes for students and early-career researchers	MSCA Programmes, regional development alliances, industry internship programmes	Creating awareness of HS value Service innovation
Industry	Industry managers and R&D practitioners	Promotion and engagement	Internships and educational programmes for industry researchers, open days for industry upon invitation, brokerage events, personal visits	Pay per service use, co-creation, service innovation

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ANNEX I.

STAKEHOLDER MAPPING FOR E-RIHS ERIC

Table I-1. Main organisations/groups identified as internal/external and primary/secondary stakeholders of the E-RIHS ERIC before its establishment.

Organisations/Groups	Internal/External	Primary/Secondary
Central Hub	Internal	P
National Nodes	Internal	P
Perspective National Nodes	External	P
Strategic Partner Organisations	External	P
Providers	Internal	P
Candidate Providers	Internal (if already user) / External	P
Users / User communities	Internal/External	P
Perspective Users / User communities	Internal (if already provider) / External	P
CH Research Institutions	External	P
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dpt. Research - Dpt. Documentation - Dpt. Data - Museum - Archives 		
Non-CH Research Institutions	External	S
Academia/Universities	External	P
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Universities - Academies 		
Repository-related Organisations (e.g., Zenodo)	External	P/S (follow up)
PID-related Organisations (e.g., ORCID)	External	P/S (follow up)
Certification/Standards Organisations and/or Communities (e.g., IIF, and ISO)	External	P/S (follow up)
National Government /Government Agencies	Internal / External depending on role	P
Regional/Provincial Governments	External	S
Local Authorities (e.g., city-level)	External	S
Research Infrastructures and Related Institutions		P/S
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ERIC and other RIs - ECCCH 	External	

Organisations/Groups	Internal/External	Primary/Secondary
International and Intergovernmental Organisations & Multilateral Agreements and Conventions	Internal (if partner) / External	P/S
Civil Society Organisations (e.g., friends/volunteers of museums)		S
Society / General Public		S
Funders / Donors		P
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public funding bodies (EU and beyond) - Private funding bodies (e.g., philanthropic foundations) 	External	
Private Sector	External	P/S
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CH/CCIS - Tourism & recreational industry - Software/hardware & equipment industries - Insurance companies - Shipping companies - Publishing companies - Scientific Journals 		
Public and Private Media/Press	External	P/S
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National TV/Radio channels - Private TV/Radio channels - Specialised press - Social media 		

Table I-1. Main individuals identified as internal/external and primary/secondary stakeholders of the E-RIHS ERIC before its establishment.

Individuals	Internal/External	Primary/Secondary
HS Researchers / Scholars	Internal / External	P/S
Non-HS Research Scholars (incl. data scientists, environmental scientists, sustainability scientists and coders)	Internal / External	P/S
Technicians	Internal	P
Administrators	Internal	P
Managers of CH Assets	External	P
Conservators		P
Curators		P
Volunteers		P/S
Representatives of National Government	Internal / External (depending on national nodes)	P
Representatives of Regional/Provincial Governments	External	P

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Individuals	Internal/External	Primary/Secondary
Representative of Local Authorities	External	P
Representative of International/Intergovernmental Organisations	Internal / External (depending on partners)	P

ANNEX II.

MARKETING-COST BREAKDOWN TEMPLATE

The Tables II-1, II-2 and II-3 provide template examples for describing the costs associated with a marketing strategy, mainly based on communication activities. The tables distinguish between electronic (Table II-1), physical communication tools (Table II-2) and printed communication materials (Table II-3). The cost analysis for the development and use of various tools should be considered when budgeting for the implementation of the marketing strategy, as this represents an essential element of effective organisation for E-RIHS.

TABLE II-1. ELECTRONIC COMMUNICATION TOOLS

	TOOL	Audience	Frequency	Cost
E - T O O L S	Online Access portal	External and Internal	On going	
	Newsletter	External and Internal	Monthly	
	Social media (e.g. LinkedIn YouTube)	External and Internal	Weekly	
	E-flyer	External and Internal	In correspondence of events	
	e-Calendar	Internal and External	Daily	
	RSS feed	Internal and External	As required by user	

TABLE II-2. PHYSICAL COMMUNICATION TOOLS

	TOOL	Audience	Frequency	Cost
P H Y S I C A L	Science & Technology Forum	External	Annual	
	Scientific Conference	External and Internal	Every two yrs	
	Industry Brokerage Events	External	Every two yrs	
	Other events	External	20 yrs	
	GA	Internal	2-3/yr	
	CNN	Internal	3-4/yr	
	WGs	Internal	8/yr	
	ERIC Launch Event	Internal	once	

TABLE II-3. PRINTED COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

	TOOL	Audience	Frequency	Cost
P R I N T E D	Booklets	External		
	Leaflet	External		
	Poster	External and Internal		
	Roll-up	External		
	Gadgets I	External		
	Gadgets II	Internal		
	Video	External	Yearly	

ANNEX III.

MONITORING FRAMEWORK TEMPLATE

The template in Table III-1 shall be adopted to shape a monitoring framework to measure the success of the implementation of the E-RIHS marketing strategy. The establishment of such a framework will fulfil the Marketing Strategy Objective #5 – MS05 (see Section § 2. *Objectives of the E-RIHS Marketing Strategy* of this document for reference).

Table III-1. Example of a template related to one of the Marketing Strategy Objectives

Objective Type <i>e.g., strategic, operational</i>	Objective Description – Verbose description of the objective <i>e.g. MS05: Strengthen the effectiveness of the E-RIHS ERIC distributed model by establishing a monitoring framework with KPIs tied to target performance values and time boundaries</i>
KPI	KPI number KPI description following SMART principles
Baseline	Value of the indicator in a specific year before the operational phase (e.g., 2025)
Target	Description of the desired status/value of the indicator at a certain moment in time of the operational phase (e.g., 2026)
Data Reporting Responsibility	Indication of the institution/person who will take on the responsibility of finding the information required and reporting on the monitoring activity (e.g., E-RIHS Central Hub)
Data Sources	Indication of the specific sources of information (e.g., annual reports, or Members, or specific section of the organisation)
Data Provider	Indication of the specific providers of information, which E-RIHS would solicit for information provision (e.g., Members or users)
Collection Methodology	Synthetic description of how the information will be collected (e.g., survey, phone calls, symposia, Service Level Agreements)

ANNEX IV.

USER-TAILORED MARKETING PLAN

E-RIHS offers a variety of services and instruments that cater to different types of stakeholders, ranging from research and education to industry and NGOs. The following marketing strategies are tailored for each stakeholder group, highlighting the E-RIHS services of interest, and indicating the most effective communication channels, the main messages and Key Performance Indicators for each tailored marketing strategies.

In the tables below (Tables IV-1—6), each stakeholder group is targeted with a strategic mix of services, communication channels, and tailored messaging to ensure that E-RIHS effectively reaches and engages its diverse audiences.

Table VI-1. Target Group: Scientific Community

SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY**Services of Interest:**

- **ARCHLAB:** Access to digital and physical archives for research.
- **DIGILAB:** Future virtual research environment for collaborative research.
- **FIXLAB:** Neutron techniques, mass spectroscopy for advanced research.
- **MOLAB:** 2D/3D analysis, remote sensing, and multi/hyper spectral imaging.
- **HS Academy:** Training and education programmes.

Marketing Communication Channels:

- **Academic Journals:** Publish articles and case studies in high-impact journals relevant to heritage science, archaeology, and conservation.
- **Conferences and Symposia:** Present at key academic conferences (e.g., European Association of Archaeologists, ICOM-CC, *International Council of Museums-International Committee for Conservation*) to showcase E-RIHS's capabilities and research opportunities.
- **Webinars and Online Workshops:** Offer free webinars on how to apply for subsidised access and use the various E-RIHS platforms.
- **Direct Email Campaigns:** Targeted emails to university departments, research institutes, and labs highlighting specific services, e.g., ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, MOLAB.

Outcome:

New collaborative projects, Service uptake, Federation of digital repositories, etc.

Marketing Strategy Objective:

MS01, MS02 (see Section § 2. *Objectives of the E-RIHS Marketing Strategy*).

KPIs (reflecting on Objective MS02):

With respect to a baseline established in the pre-operational phase, examples of relevant KPIs include increasing the number of collaborative research projects, high-impact papers, share of open access digital products published.

Table VI-2. Target Group: Service Users

SERVICE USERS

E.g., Cultural heritage institutions, museums, archives, libraries

Services of Interest:

- **ARCHLAB:** Access to comprehensive archives for research and exhibition planning.
- **DIGILAB:** Future virtual research environment for collaborative project.
- **FIXLAB:** Techniques for preservation and restoration.
- **MOLAB:** Mobile technology platforms for in-situ analysis and documentation.
- **HS Academy:** Training in conservation and preservation methods.

Marketing Communication Channels:

- **Industry Partnerships:** Collaborate with organisations (e.g., ICOM, *International Council of Museums*) to introduce E-RIHS services at workshops and meetings.
- **Institutional Newsletters:** Place information in newsletters and bulletins distributed by heritage institutions and networks.
- **Social Media:** Use platforms like LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube and specialised forums (e.g., Museum Next) to reach heritage professionals with case studies and success stories.
- **On-site Demonstrations:** Offer live demonstrations of MOLAB technologies during special exhibitions or restoration projects.

Outcome:

Skills development, Creating awareness of HS value, Service innovation, etc.

Marketing Strategy Objective:

MS03, MS04 (see Section § 2. *Objectives of the E-RIHS Marketing Strategy*).

Examples of relevant KPIs include:

Consumption of available units of access; acknowledgements of E-RIHS in RI users' publications/dissemination, new collaborations established, etc.

Table VI-3. Target Group: NGOs, International/Intergovernmental Organisations

NGOs, INTERNATIONAL/INTERGOVERNMENTAL ORGANISATIONS**Services of Interest:**

- **ARCHLAB:** Archives for research and project documentation.
- **DIGILAB:** Future virtual research environment for collaborative projects at global scale.
- **MOLAB:** Tools for on-site heritage assessment and conservation.
- **HS Academy:** Training programs for capacity building.

Marketing Communication Channels:

- **NGO Newsletters:** Feature E-RIHS in newsletters and reports distributed by international heritage bodies.
- **Workshops and Capacity-Building Sessions:** Conduct training workshops and seminars to build local capacity in regions where these NGOs operate.
- **Engaging with high-level networks** such as UNESCO and Europa Nostra to integrate E-RIHS services into ongoing conservation projects;
- **Grant Programs:** Collaborate on grant proposals, offering E-RIHS services as in-kind contributions to heritage conservation initiatives.

Outcome:

Joint initiatives, visibility in high-level initiatives and at events.

Marketing Strategy Objective:

MS02 (see Section § 2. *Objectives of the E-RIHS Marketing Strategy*).

Examples of relevant KPIs include:

N. Formal agreements/Memoranda of Understanding; N. joint initiatives.

Table VI-4. Target Group: Educational Institutions and Students

EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS AND STUDENTS

Services of Interest:

- **HS Academy:** Open access to training and educational resources.
- **ARCHLAB:** Archives for academic research.
- **DIGILAB:** Future access to digital tools.
- **FIXLAB & MOLAB:** Research opportunities through subsidised access.

Marketing Communication Channels:

- **University Collaborations:** Partner with universities to incorporate E-RIHS services into curricula and offer internships or research opportunities.
- **Social Media:** Use Instagram, Twitter, and Facebook to engage students with interactive content, tutorials, and success stories from peers.
- **Online Learning Platforms:** Offer free courses and certifications through platforms like Coursera, edX, or directly on E-RIHS's website.
- **Academic Fairs and Open Days:** Participate in university fairs and open days to present E-RIHS's offerings directly to students.

Outcome:

Pay per service use, Co-creation, Service innovation, Partnerships, etc.

Marketing Strategy Objective:

MS02, MS03, MS04 (see Section § 2. *Objectives of the E-RIHS Marketing Strategy*)

Examples of relevant KPIs include:

N. events organised with/for education organisations; N. Alliances/Agreements with educational institutes; N. certifications awarded.

Table VI-5. Target Group: Policy Makers

POLICY MAKERS

E.g., EU, national, regional and local levels

Services of Interest:

- **HS/CH-related Policy shaping consultation**
- **Contribution to EOSC Implementation**

Marketing Communication Channels:

- **Policy Briefings:** Regularly issue policy briefs that highlight how E-RIHS's research and tools can support cultural heritage preservation and inform policy decisions.
- **Government Conferences and Workshops:** Present at governmental and EU-level conferences focused on cultural heritage and innovation.
- **Direct Engagement:** Engage with policy makers through direct meetings, presentations, and roundtables to discuss how E-RIHS services align with policy objectives and orientate funding trends.
- **Newsletters and Reports:** Distribute tailored newsletters and reports to policymakers, showcasing case studies where E-RIHS's work has influenced policy.

Outcome:

Influence on policy shaping, influence on project calls.

Marketing Strategy Objective:

MS02 (see Section § 2. *Objectives of the E-RIHS Marketing Strategy*).

Examples of relevant KPIs include:

N. Participation in policy fora; N. Project calls awarded.

Table VI-6. Target Group: General Public

<p>GENERAL PUBLIC</p> <p>Services of Interest:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• HS Academy: Educational resources and public lectures.• MOLAB: Public demonstrations and exhibitions using mobile technologies.• DIGILAB: Potential future access to virtual tours and educational platforms. <p>Marketing Communication Channels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Social Media: Engage the public through platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube with educational content, virtual tours, and behind-the-scenes looks at conservation projects.• Public Events: Host public lectures, exhibitions, and open days where MOLAB’s mobile technology can be demonstrated.• Educational Campaigns: Collaborate with schools and community organizations to create educational programs that introduce heritage science to younger audiences.• Media Outreach: Use traditional media (TV, radio, newspapers) to reach broader audiences with stories about E-RIHS’s impact on cultural heritage preservation. <p>Outcome:</p> <p>Social media engagement</p> <p>Marketing Strategy Objective:</p> <p>MS0, MS04 (see Section § 2. <i>Objectives of the E-RIHS Marketing Strategy</i>)</p> <p>Examples of relevant KPIs include:</p> <p>N. communications events, N. Citizens engaged, Social media share of engagement.</p>
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